

Computational Bamboo: Digital and vernacular design principles for the construction of a temporary bending-active structure

Seiichi Suzuki¹, Evy L.M. Slabbinck¹ and Jan Knippers¹

¹ Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design (ITKE)
s.suzuki@itke.uni-stuttgart.de

Abstract. Active bending is calling for a paradigm shift in the way structures are designed and built. It is in this context that natural materials, like bamboo, can play a significant role in the development of more sustainable and economical material practices in architecture. Here, we present the results of a two-weeks workshop held in Quito, Ecuador, that lead to the design and construction of a bending-active demonstrator entirely built with natural materials. The structure was designed by using a highly intuitive numerically form-finding approach and materialized by only employed locally processed bamboo materials and natural jute cords. This implies not only a more sustainable construction practice derived from the usage of these materials and the lack of complex formworks and high-end machinery but also a more environmentally friendly deconstruction stage where all materials constituting the structure can be recycled. The presented study serves to strategically showcase what is suggested to be called a digital vernacular approach for the design of bending-active systems.

Keywords: Active bending, Bamboo, Computational Design.

1 Introduction

Lightweight design principles have been formulated on the promise of an improved material practice to deal with a truly sustainable development of our physical environment. Over the past years, the research on bending-active structures has gained in importance given their inherent link between form and structure. The aim has been to create more efficient constructions in which a compromise between strength and lightness is built from the generation of an optimized geometry. In this way, a more sustainable and intelligent design practice can be established that looks for minimizing the consumption of materials and energy resources as well as the footprint of building constructions. Major efforts for the exploration of these design principles have been developed on the basis of rapid advances on composites technologies and computer-based technologies for design and fabrication. However, the problem in this modern discourse of sustainable development is that composites are still mostly engineered as fossil-based materials and the use of computational techniques tends to avoid the

integration of more local design principles and technology constraints. Therefore, it is becoming particularly interesting to investigate the emerging design potentials that these bending-active systems have when the relative high-tech technology required for its production is replaced with low-tech technology and locally available natural materials, and when parametric and numerical strategies are tailored for these purposes.

In this paper, we present the results of the design and construction of a bending-active demonstrator using the elastic properties of bamboo that was built in Quito at Museum of Interactive Science (MIC). The structure was developed in the context of the Global Summer School Program of Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia that was organized in collaboration with Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design (ITKE) and the Pontifical Catholic University of Ecuador (PUCE). The workshop focused on the exploration of non-standard topological articulations of bending-active bamboo elements when shaping a structural system. The development of this structure was entirely based on the use of local materials through highly intuitive design processes that allowed to explore solutions beyond traditional typologies. The workshop aimed to open a discussion regarding lightweight structures and its role for the sustainable development of our building environment.

2 Fundamentals

Over the last years, a renewed interest has been reported on the study of active bending as a forming principle for self-stabilizing structural components through elastic deformation. By inducing curvature on initially straight elements, bending-active structures can be designed to develop complex freeform geometries with load-bearing capacities. The main requirement is the use of materials with high strength and low bending stiffness which makes fiber reinforced polymers ideal (FRP) (Kotelnikova-Weiler et al. 2013, Lienhard 2014). Even if active bending is playing a key role in the development of more sustainable design practices, an inherent conflict is created because the disposal of composites materials has a greater impact in our physical environment. Moreover, access to many semi-finished FRP products, like pultruded rods, is still difficult in certain areas due to the high-end machinery required for its production.

For a long time, active bending principles were used as an economic construction technique for producing curved elements in vernacular architectures mainly by nomadic people (Lienhard et al. 2013). Its utilization is therefore not restricted to modern composite materials. Frei Otto and his multidisciplinary research team at the University of Stuttgart utilized the generic term curved compression arches to describe those structures that are shaped from elastically bent bamboo (Gass et al. 1985). Further studies were conducted by Gernot Minke at the University of Kassel where different domed-like and hyperbolic structural solutions based on the experimental use of elastically bent bamboo laths were developed in Guatemala and Colombia with the collaboration of local universities (Minke 2012). By the end of 2006, two experimental elastic gridshells utilizing bamboo laths were developed in Germany by Auwi Stübbe

and his students (Minke 2012) that later served as inspiration for the development of the collaborative Cocoon project led by the Aarhus School of Architecture (Hansen and Kim 2016). In both cases, the design was entirely driven by experimental studies on scaled models that, in the case of the Cocoon project, also served to inform the construction of a computational model based on T-Splines. From a digital perspective, special attention demands the ZCS Bamboo Pavilion and the textile hybrid amphitheater built in Xingu, Brazil. Built-in 2015 as a large-span elastic gridshell in Hong Kong, the ZCS Bamboo pavilion was developed from exhaustive experimental studies on different scaled physical models that were used to gradually calibrate numerical models based on particle methods (Crolla 2017). For the second project, physical models were in turn used to inform numerical models based on the Updated Reference Method (Seixas et al. 2017). Both projects employed elastically bent bamboo rods and showcased strategies for addressing the use of natural materials within numerical strategies.

3 Materials

Bamboo is a grass plant with a hard outer layer and a soft inner part that makes it strong as wood but much more flexible and lighter. Considering that bamboo is a fast-growing natural resource with minimum environmental impact, its use as a building material can be classified as sustainable. The material has a high resistance to tension and an average bending strength twice as strong as most convention structural timber (Minke 2012). Bamboo was also classified as an ideal material for bending-active and even elastic kinetics (Lienhard 2014). In this context, different considerations need to be taken when employing the elastic properties of bamboo. In its natural form, the minimum bending radius of canes requires larger spans for increasing the geometric curvature of the structure as in the case of the ZCS Bamboo Pavilion. In case that more flexibility is required, canes can be split into laths by introducing cuts parallel to the direction of fibers. The challenge in both cases is to control structural and geometrical behaviors derived from the use of a natural material with heterogeneous properties.

Fig. 1. Local production of bamboo laths. **a)** Splitting process of the canes, **b)** Sanding process of the laths. Image courtesy of the International Bamboo and Rattan Organization – Regional Office for Latin America and the Caribbean.

For the development of this project, material flexibility was pushed to its limits to facilitate the exploration of non-standard topologic networks of actively-bent elements. In doing so, we focused on combining advanced computational techniques with a locally sustainable construction practice. For these reasons, we decided to work with laths and rods made of bamboo that were produced near the construction site (**Fig. 1**). These semi-finished products were cut with a length of 3 meters from *Phyllostachys* canes. Laths have a solid rectangular cross-section of 1 by 5 centimeters that are directly sanded with machinery for homogenization. Rods have a circular cross-section of 1 centimeter that is produced by splitting laths and applying a similar sanding process.

Due to the short time of workshop and the lack of test equipment, the amount of permissible bending and torsion was evaluated by hand-bending the material until failure. The aim was to acquire an empirical knowledge of material's behaviors permitting to intuitively calibrate the design tools. Through these simple tests, we concluded that laths were more flexible than rods and that their use within the structure must be differentiated (**Fig. 2**). In any case, the relative cross-sectional homogeneity of both materials showed that a relatively good approximation of the elastic curve can be reached if we considered that we are using a natural material. Nevertheless, the significant disadvantage was that rods exhibited a quick failure if they were bent beyond the established limits. All this empirical information was then directly used to inform the computational design process.

Fig. 2. Empirical material tests for determining the minimum bending radius.

4 Architectural concept

The structure was conceived as an experimental demonstrator called “Computational Bamboo” that was framed under the idea of computationally rethinking vernacular design principles utilizing the elastic deformation of natural materials. The constraint given by the MIC was to develop the design of the bamboo structure within a medium-sized interior hall of 7.5 by 20 meters without affecting its regular operations. This hall

had no specific function and is mostly been used for circulation purposes between three exhibition areas. The proposed design aimed to channel this circulation by strengthening the entrance to the hall and providing a sitting area for visitors. For this reason, the structure may be perceived as two connected entities unfolded from a single body. The larger part of the structure called the “roof” was designed as a canopy that permits to channel the main circulations from the galleries to the hall (**Fig. 3**). The “roof” is floating above the people and only touches the ground in two points. The second part was defined as a “wall” and is integrated with a sitting feature. The wall is denser from material and should indicate more privacy and comfort.

Fig. 3. “Computational Bamboo” structure.

The design of the structure was carried from a continuously curved edge beam that freely extended throughout the entire volume of the hall. The curvature of this element was derived from elastic deformations that were occasioned by the introduction of several fixation points (supports) along its entire length. By correctly adjusting the positions of these fixations, deformations were programmed to fulfill the initial design intentions. In doing so, the edge-beam was forced to self-intersect to produce a pair of interconnected closed loops (Fig. 4). Each loop constituted a different part of the structure and was filled with a unique pattern of actively bent elements. This filling pattern (so-called syntax), inspired by basket weaving, was designed as a network of interconnected curves with segments where high curvature was concentrated. Under these circumstances, the materialization of these patterns called for the use of bamboo laths due to its greater flexibility and asymmetric cross-section. This condition that was not so critical for the materialization of the edge-beam in which its extension and curvature allowed to use the less flexible bamboo rods. The asymmetrical cross-section of the laths enabled a geometric spatial change in torsion (Slabbinck et al. 2017) for creating structural depth and geometrical stiffness, as well as an easy flat connection to the edge-beam. It also permitted the creation of vertical connections on the center ring of the "roof" so that the weak axis allowed to be bent while following the global curvature of the structure. In addition, there is the structural depth and the gain of geometrical stiffness to the structure. At the end, the entire structure was 15.5 m long, spanned 7.5 meters across the museum hall and reached a height of 4m at its peak.

Fig. 4. Conceptual scheme of the different parts of the structure.

5 Computational design

Given the different architectural requirements, a multi-step modeling workflow was developed to conduct the design of the curved edge-beam and the inner-filled patterns. Results from an in-house real-time physically-based modeling software called ElasticSpace were exchanged with the Grasshopper (McNeel and Associates 2019a) environment of the Rhinoceros CAD (McNeel and Associates 2019b) package to gradually refine the entire geometry and topological arrangement of the structure. ElasticSpace was developed as a specialized form-finding application for the design of bending-active and textile hybrid systems based on the continuous manipulation of topological spaces during numerical integration (Suzuki and Knippers 2017). This form-finding strategy tries to replicate the empirical and experimental experience of playing with physical materials to derive structural forms to enhance the interactivity of numerical models when used as design tools. The principal aim is to bridge the gap between analog and digital design practices and, therefore, stimulates the development of novel structural typologies (Suzuki and Knippers 2018). Considering that most of the students of the workshop didn't have previous experience on the use of parametric or numerical tools, it was also proven that this strategy was highly adequate for introducing new practitioners to the realm of simulation-based design.

Fig. 5. Explorative studies of the edge-beam conducted with ElasticSpace

The topological and geometrical exploration of the edge-beam was entirely conducted with ElasticSpace (**Fig. 5**). Polylines with embedded physics representing the bamboo rods of 3 meters were dynamically/interactively added, deleted and connected during this process to gradually shape the entire curved edge that, in the end, resulted in a total length of 51 meters. The edge-beam stiffness of the numerical model was calibrated with the information extracted from physical tests. The simulation started without any type of topologic condition because this one gradually evolved throughout time. At any time of the process, the “dead” geometry (model without physics) of the hall can be visualized to facilitate the evaluation of the aesthetic

properties and functional requirements. Because the continuous edge-beam was gradually shaped by adding new elements to the simulation, the database of the numerical model is composed of multiple digital “rods” storing the information of its physical counterparts. Regarding this condition, it is important to add that all topological operations shaping the system were time-dependent. Thus, it was relatively easy to extract the assembly sequence logic of the edge-beam from the database of the numerical model.

When reaching a mature solution, all the geometric and topological information was saved in an XML file that was later used to reconstruct the geometry in Grasshopper with a custom plugin permitting the communication with ElasticSpace. Different studies to generate the filling patterns were then conducted on the basis of this non-physical representation of the edge-beam. Contrary to previous modeling requirements in which extended geometrical and topological freedom was desired to explore the design space fully, the generation of inner patterns within the predefined boundaries demanded a stricter control of the modeling process through associative logics. Two specific patterns were developed for both looped areas with specific syntaxes of connectivity. For the “roof”, the filling pattern was generated from curves with endpoints lying on the loop and with a path revolved around an attraction point that was positioned inside the loop (**Fig. 6a**). The location of this point and the size of the revolved path were parametrically designed according to architectural intents. On the other hand, the pattern of the “wall” had a more straightforward logic with curves connected through shifted sequences. In both cases, the intersections of the curves determined the discretization of the further physical model.

Fig. 6. Digital model – a) Generation of the “roof” filling pattern b) Final form-found geometry

At this point, filling patterns were modeled with “dead” geometry, and only the edge-beam was physically modeled. The ElasticSpace plugin for Grasshopper also included a numerical solver that was then used to run the form-finding of the complete structure (**Fig. 6b**). That is, the edge-beam was form-found again with the influence of the deformation of filling patterns. It is important to note that at this time, some behavioral considerations, like the torsional effects on the laths, were not considered within the numerical model to simplify the design process. With the form-found geometry, the final stage of the workflow was to develop a digital model entirely oriented to inform the construction of the structure (**Fig. 7a-b**).

Fig. 7. Construction information for the **a)** “roof” and **b)** “wall” extracted from the digital model. The diagrams show the labeling of laths and the different connection points.

The entire form-finding approach enables a full spatial design of the elastic grid shell. Most elastic gridshells are based on an orthogonal pattern (syntax) and an arch typology that is supported by a 2D edge with the exceptions of some openings. One can argue that these grid shells are 2.5D, and this is mainly due to their erecting process. Some built examples like the Asymptotic gridshell (Schling et al. 2018) made a step in a more spatial approach to make the edge beam /perimeter a design parameter. The demonstrator showcases the 3D design and the complex syntax enabled by the simulation tool.

6 Construction process

The edge-beam was assembled on-site by connecting shorter segments each one made of three rods that were bundled together to obtain the required stiffness for holding up the structure. For this, an important consideration was that the position of rods needed to be alternated to avoid having two connections at the same place and thus causing a weak point for kinking. Bamboo rods were then tied together with a natural jute burlap cord through a high tension knotting system that is traditionally used in bamboo constructions (**Fig. 8**). The connection had to be firm in tension and compression, but as well in rotation around 3-axes as every joint was unique and had different forces to transfer. The distance of the connection to the seam line and the way of tightening were two parameters that were optimized by empirical testing. As there was no weaker axis due to the circular cross-section and the high bending stiffness of the rods, these details had to be adapted during construction several times. The edge-beam was then erected by using a temporary scaffolding with a minimum number of bamboo struts for stabilization.

Fig. 8. Tests for connecting between the lath and the edge-beam.

At the same time, the construction process of the filling patterns started with measuring all the bamboo laths we received. In this process, we realized that not all the material had an expected length of 3 meters. This condition was problematic because laths needed to be connected sequentially to shape longer elements for assembling both patterns. Here, it was clear that multiple connections would accumulate local errors regarding the length of laths and finally produce a shorter element. To address this issue, all laths were classified on the basis of common lengths. This new information was used to update the entire model for the construction process. On this basis, new assembly logics were generated that permitted to produce those longer elements by efficiently combining the available material. Here, pre-construction planning and labeling was a key aspect. Bamboo laths were attached with the same burlap cord and the end of some laths were pre-drilled with a hole to facilitate the connection with the edge-beam. It was important for laths that the cord prevented lateral movements and rotations at all times.

Finally, these longer lath elements were inserted one by one into the system by following a woven logic (**Fig. 9**). They were positioned and fixed on the markers of the edge-beam, and then guided in the desired bending and torsional direction. Once the connections between the laths were fixed, the bamboo struts were progressively removed. The structure got later attached to the bench, which gave extra stability. After the exhibition period of six months, the structure was disassembled, and all the components were recycled for further use. After disassembly, rods didn't show significant creep deformation compared to laths in which the amount of deformation was entirely associated with their relative local position within the structure.

Fig. 9. Woven insertion logic for laths.

7 Summary

With rapid advances in simulation technology and composites materials, innovative design practices have been developed for the exploration of design solutions based on active bending. These lightweight design principles may be, to a certain extent, compromised by the use of oil-based materials when framed under the idea of a more sustainable material practice. Also, the use of computer-based technologies for design and fabrication tends to avoid the integration of local principles linked with the needs of specific regions. It should be noted that, even before the advent of composites and computer technology, active bending principles have been empirically utilized with natural materials to economically produce curved elements.

In this context, the efforts presented in this paper were focused on investigating the emerging design potentials that may derive from the combination of advanced computing techniques and locally available natural materials for bending-active structure. During a two-week workshop, a large-scale demonstrator using the elastic

properties of bamboo was designed and fabricated. A multi-step modeling workflow based on highly interactive form-finding processes served to push the elastic properties of bamboo to its limits by developing a design beyond traditional typologies. The structure consisted of a continuous bending-active edge-beam, made out of rods, with some regions filled with specific bending-active patterns, made out of laths. All materials were produced from local bamboo canes and processed to create a smooth consistent structural element. Avoiding the use of any type of synthetic material, all the joints of the structure were solved through a traditional friction-tight rope connection with natural jute cord. As a result, we may categorize this type of structures in which the geometrical and topological complexity is computationally generated on the basis of natural material constraints, as digital vernacular typologies within the research on bending-active structures.

Acknowledgements

Computational Bamboo was a demonstrator developed during the Global Summer School program of the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC) in Quito, Ecuador, which was organized in close collaboration with the Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design (ITKE, Prof. Jan Knippers). The authors would like to thank the technical support offered by Yaner Luis Cangá Chavez, Andres Obregon, and Juan Edison Columba Paucar, and volunteers Byron Esteban Cadena Campos, Sophia Natalia Gualán Chacón, Gustavo Francisco Abdo Hernández, Santiago Dario Guevara Hidalgo, Karen Elizabeth Landazuri Proaño, Rafael Fernando Suárez Molina, Santiago Gabriel Miño Paz, and Nestor Emmanuel Mendoza Zambrano.

This project received great support from the Museum of Interactive Science (MIC), Pontifical Catholic University of Ecuador (PUCE), the International Bamboo and Rattan Organization – Regional Office for Latin America and the Caribbean (INBAR), Sustainable Forest Management Corporation (Comafors), Fablab Zoi, Museum of Interactive Science (MIC), CODESA, Fibrobambu, and funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 642877 and Pelikano Plywood.

The presented research was conducted on the intersection between research and teaching together with students of the IAAC GSS Quito Programme. The authors would like to express their gratitude towards: Juan Francisco Mayorga Jaramillo, Valeria Latorre, Gordon Leibowitz, Valeria León, Veronica Sofia Molina, Maria Gabriela Chacon Palacios, Gisella Parra, Fausto Andres Davila Pazmiño, and Juan David Barona Trujillo.

References

1. Crolla, K.: Building indeterminacy modelling – the 'ZCB Bamboo Pavilion' as a case study on nonstandard construction from natural materials *Vis. in Eng.* **5**(1), 178 (2017). doi: 10.1186/s40327-017-0051-4

2. Gass, S., Drüsedau, H., Hennicke, J., Dunkelberg, K.: *Bambus: Bamboo*. IL, vol. 31. Institut für Leichte Flächentragwerke Universität Stuttgart, Stuttgart (1985)
3. Hansen, L., Kim, S.: 'COCOON' a bamboo building with integration of digital design and low-tech construction *Structures and Architecture*. London, UK., 1159–1165 (2016)
4. Kotelnikova-Weiler, N., Douthe, C., Hernandez, E.L., Baverel, O., Gengnagel, C., Caron, J.-F.: Materials for Actively-Bent Structures *International Journal of Space Structures* **28**(3-4), 229–240 (2013). doi: 10.1260/0266-3511.28.3-4.229
5. Lienhard, J.: Bending-active structures: Form-finding strategies using elastic deformation in static and kinetic systems and the structural potentials therein. *Forschungsberichte aus dem Institut für Tragkonstruktionen und Konstruktives Entwerfen, Universität Stuttgart*, vol. 36. ITKE, Stuttgart (2014)
6. Lienhard, J., Alpermann, H., Gengnagel, C., Knippers, J.: Active Bending: A review on structures where Bending is used as a Self-Formation Process *International Journal of Space Structures* **28**(3&4), 187–196 (2013)
7. McNeel, R., Associates: Grasshopper. <https://www.grasshopper3d.com/> (2019a)
8. McNeel, R., Associates: Rhinoceros. <https://www.mcneel.com/> (2019b)
9. Minke, G.: *Building with bamboo*. Birkhäuser, Basel (2012)
10. Schling, E., Kilian, M., Wang, H., Schikore, J., Pottmann, H.: Design and Construction of Curved Support Structures with Repetitive Parameters *Advances in Architectural Geometry*. Gothenburg, Sweden. (2018)
11. Seixas, M., Bina, J., Stoffel, P., Ripper, J.L., Moreira, L.E., Ghavami, K.: Active Bending and Tensile Pantographic Bamboo Hybrid Amphitheater Structure *Journal IASS* **58**(3), 239–252 (2017). doi: 10.20898/j.iass.2017.193.872
12. Slabbinck, E.L.M., Körner, A., Knippers, J.: Torsion as a design driver in plate-bending-active tensile structures *Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium 2017: Interfaces: Architecture, Engineering, Science*. Hamburg, Germany. (2017)
13. Suzuki, S., Knippers, J.: ElasticSpace: A computational framework for interactive form-finding of textile hybrid structures through evolving topology networks *International Journal of Parallel, Emergent and Distributed Systems* **32**(sup1), S4-S14 (2017). doi: 10.1080/17445760.2017.1390101
14. Suzuki, S., Knippers, J.: Digital Vernacular Design: Form-finding at the edge of realities Recalibration. On imprecision and infidelity. *Proceedings of the 38th Annual Conference of the Association for Computer Aided Design in Architecture (ACADIA)*. Mexico City, Mexico. (2018)